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Understanding the time-driven shifts of vaccine effectiveness against any and severe COVID-19 before and after the surge of Omicron variants within 2.5 years of vaccination: A meta-regression

Marek Petráš^{1,*}, Daniela Janovská¹, Danuše Lomozová¹, Martina Franklová¹, Pavel Dlouhý², Jozef Rosina^{3,6}, Ivana Králová Lesná^{4,5}

¹ Department of Epidemiology and Biostatistics, Third Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

² Department of Hygiene, Third Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

³ Department of Medical Biophysics and Informatics, Third Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

⁴ Laboratory for Atherosclerosis Research, Centre for Experimental Medicine, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic

⁵ Department of Anesthesia and Intensive Medicine, First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University and University Military Hospital, Prague, Czech Republic

⁶ Department of Health Care and Population Protection, Faculty of Biomedical Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague, Kladno, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: The COVID-19 pandemic required rapid development of vaccines within a short period of time which did not allow to assess vaccine effectiveness (VE) in the long-term.

Methods: A computerized literature search was undertaken to identify eligible studies, with no language restrictions, published between 1 December 2020 and 30 June 2023.

Results: Out of a total of 27,597 publications, 761 studies were included. Early VE of 87.2% decreased to 55.1% after 9 months among populations fully immunized not only with mRNA (proxy mRNA) vaccines, and 66.3% decreased to 23.5% in populations immunized exclusively with non-mRNA vaccines. Protection against severe COVID-19 declined to 80.9% for proxy mRNA vaccines and 67.2% for non-mRNA vaccines. Omicron variants significantly diminished VE. Within 6–8 months of receiving a single booster of an mRNA vaccine, VE declined to 14.0% and 67.7% for any and severe COVID-19, respectively. Multiple mRNA booster doses restored protection that declined to 29.5% and 70.6% for any and severe COVID-19, respectively, within 5–7 months.

Conclusion: Outcomes of this meta-regression underscore the evolving nature of COVID-19 in response to vaccination, dosing schedules, and emerging variants, and provide crucial insights for public health interventions and vaccination strategies.

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Introduction

The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic necessitated the implementation of specific measures to minimize its impact on global public health. Nonpharmaceutical precautions played a crucial role in preventing the massive spread of SARS-CoV-2 [1]. However, it was widely recognized that only widespread and global vaccination could effectively bring the virus under control [2]. The rapid development of various types of vaccines, supported by numerous countries and international organizations, was successfully com-

pleted within less than a year, enabling the commencement of widespread vaccination of the world's population in December 2020 [3].

Various vaccine types, utilizing both new and original technologies, have been developed to combat the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. These vaccines include those based on novel mRNA technology, nonreplicating adenoviruses, and traditional whole-virus inactivation or subunit recombinant protein. The first vaccines received emergency use authorization from both major regulators of the USA (Food and Drug Administration) and the European Union (European Medicines Agency), followed by the World Health Organization [2,4].

The efficacy of vaccines, as determined in short-term clinical trials, was confirmed by the rapid decline in new cases of COVID-19 in the real-world setting regardless of its severity [5,6].

* Corresponding author. Marek Petráš, Department of Epidemiology and Biostatistics, Third Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Ruská 87, 100 00 Prague, Czech Republic.

E-mail address: marek.petras@lf3.cuni.cz (M. Petráš).

However, over time, the original ancestral SARS-CoV-2 variant was replaced by new variants, some of which posed a threat even to the vaccinated population [7,8]. It became evident that a new potential surge could only be mitigated through multiple-dose booster immunization using either monovalent or bivalent vaccines containing an additional component targeting the Omicron variants [9,10].

Numerous observational studies, including meta-analyses, have sought to address the question of how long postvaccination protection can actually persist. Their findings suggested that breakthrough infections were not only caused by new circulating variants but, also, by the waning protection acquired through vaccination [11,12]. Given the diverse nature of these studies, an overarching assessment utilizing quantitative synthesis was required.

Given the above, we conceived, designed and conducted a comprehensive study referred to as “meta-COVANESS” (META-analysis/regression of COVid VAccine effectiveNESS), which primarily focused on assessing the level of protection afforded by COVID-19 immunization. The main objective of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of any COVID-19 vaccine over a period of 2.5 years since vaccination, with the first results published last year [13]. Studies published to date enabled us to present up-to-date results regarding the time-dependent protection conferred by both full and boosted immunization with mRNA and non-mRNA vaccines. To eliminate confounding factors, we employed a meta-regression model to determine real-world vaccine effectiveness (VE).

Material and methods

This study was carried out following the guidelines of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) and the Meta-analysis Of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (MOOSE) [14–16]. These guidelines facilitated the assessment of the quality of relevant studies and enabled a quantitative synthesis of the outcomes (Supplementary Tables 1S, 2S, and 3S). The meta-COVANESS study was registered in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews under registration number CRD42022301503.

Literature search

A comprehensive search of the pertinent literature was conducted using the MEDLINE and Excerpta Medica dataBASE (EMBASE) databases, along with MedRxiv, an open-access online repository for complete preprints of unpublished manuscripts. The eligibility criteria for inclusion required the studies to have been published between 1 December 2020 and 30 June 2023, without any language restrictions. Additionally, daily searches of MEDLINE via PubMed Really Simple Syndication (RSS) feeds were performed throughout the same period. Moreover, a manual recursive search of references in published reviews, meta-analyses, and the database of International Vaccine Access Center was carried out to identify any additional relevant studies beyond the computerized search [17].

Study selection

Publications were selected based on their keywords and synonyms, including terms such as immunization, COVID-19, and effectiveness (Supplementary Table 4S). Eligible studies had to meet the following inclusion criteria: (1) observational studies; (2) a control or reference group represented by unvaccinated participants; (3) exposure defined by type-specific or commercial vaccines, including the number of administered doses; (4) the outcome assessed by COVID-19 disease of any symptomatology and

severity; and (5) stated vaccine effectiveness (VE) with the appropriate confidence interval (CI). The primary outcome of this study aimed to determine time-dependent VE in two distinct periods: before and during the incidence of Omicron variants. Variant-undetermined estimates were assessed as a subcategory of variants in the meta-regression.

Data extraction

Estimates including the 95% CI were obtained directly from eligible studies and, if unavailable, they were imputed from the stated effect sizes (ES), i.e., odds ratio, hazard ratio, risk ratio, or incidence rate ratio. Postvaccination time associated with the estimates was meticulously extracted, and any time-independent estimates were aggregated into a time-unspecific group.

Moreover, estimates assigned to parameters, including the demographic characteristics of the study population such as sex and age groups, specific population segments, prior SARS-CoV-2 infection status, and the incidence of coronavirus variants, were extracted. To ensure a comprehensive analysis, VE estimates were further categorized based on the following factors: type of vaccines utilized within the population (either various types including mRNA vaccines or only non-mRNA vaccines types), number of vaccine doses received (partial, full, booster, and multiple-booster immunization), homologous vaccination (matching the previous vaccine type with the last one), and unvaccinated reference group (stratified into vaccine-naïve individuals, previously infected participants, and proxy unvaccinated subjects). A detailed categorization of the above variables is provided in Supplementary Table 5S.

Quality assessment

To evaluate the quality of the studies, data regarding the study characteristics, participants, interventions, comparisons, and outcomes were extracted. The Newcastle-Ottawa Quality Assessment Scale (NOS) was used to assess study quality across three domains: selection of participants, comparability of vaccinated and unvaccinated groups, and outcome assessment, with the results expressed as a risk of bias (RoB) [13,18]. For this meta-regression analysis, studies with a score of ≥ 8 stars were considered high-quality, those with 5–7 stars were categorized as moderate-quality, and studies with ≤ 4 stars were deemed low-quality ones. These categories of study quality were also utilized as additional variables in the meta-regression outcome.

To minimize the impact of confounding factors, the analysis assessed adjusted/matched and crude estimates. As studies reported in non-peer-reviewed journals (e.g., preprints or posters) might carry a higher risk of bias compared to those published in peer-reviewed journals, the variable of article source was included to account for this potential bias. Further details are provided in Supplementary Table 5S.

Data analysis

Time-dependent outcome was determined based on absolute VE obtained from the meta-regression model. The estimates extracted from the source studies were converted into effect size (ES) using the formula $1 - VE/100$. The regression model utilized log-transformed ES and standard errors (SE) calculated from both limits of the 95% CI using a metric that closely approximated the normal distribution. While the ES and upper limit were always consistent with the source values, an acceptable deviation of the lower limit was set to be $< |\pm 0.05|$ compared to the value declared by the study.

Time-dependent VE was calculated separately for each month following partial, full, booster, and multiple-booster immunization.

Figure 1. Flowchart. VE, vaccine effectiveness; CI, confidence interval.

The VE rates were assessed for both the pre-Omicron and Omicron variants in proxy mRNA and non-mRNA vaccinated populations. The meta-regression assessing VE against any COVID-19 disease (of any symptomatology and/or severity) and VE against severe disease (hospitalization and/or death) was conducted with mutual adjustment of the following variables: specific population type, age groups, homologous vaccination, previous infection, specific reference group of unvaccinated participants, study quality, and the use of estimate adjustment.

The outcomes were assigned to the general population of adults immunized with a homologous vaccine and no previous infection who participated in high-quality studies with adjusted estimates published in peer-reviewed journals. Statistical analyses were performed using STATA version 17.0 (StataCorp. 2021. Stata Statistical Software, College Station, TX, USA) with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ with a two-tailed 95% CI.

Results

A total of 27,597 publications were identified, out of which 26,836 were excluded due to irrelevant or duplicated studies and the absence of inclusion criteria (Figure 1, Supplementary Table 6S). The inclusion criteria were satisfied by 761 eligible studies that yielded 14,985 estimates related to COVID-19 of varying severity, including infection, disease, hospitalization, or death. The number of time-dependent estimates, along with the associated studies, is detailed in Supplementary Tables 7S, 8S, 9S, 10S and 11S.

Full immunization

The VE rates for any COVID-19 were lower than those for severe disease, with the difference particularly pronounced among individuals fully immunized with non-mRNA vaccines. However, these rates demonstrated a time-dependent decline irrespective of disease severity and vaccine type (Figure 2, Supplementary Table 7S). The initial effectiveness of 87.2% (95% CI: 86.9-87.4%) against any COVID-19 declined to 55.1% (95% CI: 53.7-56.4%) at 9 months after proxy mRNA vaccination during the prevalence of pre-Omicron variants. A similar decline was observed in non-mRNA vaccinated individuals, i.e., from 66.3% (95% CI: 63.2-69.1%) to 23.5% (95% CI: 4.0-39.0%). During the same 9-month period, VE against severe COVID-19 decreased more gradually from 93.5% (95% CI: 93.1-93.9%) to 80.9% (95% CI: 78.5-82.9%) in proxy mRNA-vaccinated individuals and from 88.2% (95% CI: 86.3-89.8%) to 67.2% (95% CI: 60.2-73.0%) in non-mRNA vaccinated individuals.

The surge of Omicron variants significantly diminished early VE against both any and severe COVID-19 regardless of the type of vaccine. The VE against any disease declined from 53.9% (95% CI: 50.3-57.2%) to 11.6% (95% CI: 5.6-17.1%) and from 33.5% (95% CI: 18.7-45.6%) to 8.3% (95% CI: 0.1-16.0%) within 6 months of proxy mRNA and non-mRNA vaccination, respectively. Over the same 6-month period, protection related to hospitalization or death decreased from 84.1% (95% CI: 80.6-87.0%) to 61.1% (95% CI: 56.0-65.7%) following proxy mRNA vaccination, and from 80.1% (95% CI: 76.2-83.3%) to 62.1% (95% CI: 56.3-67.1%) after non-mRNA vaccination. These protection rates remained at a level of 34.8% (95%

Figure 2. Time-dependent vaccine effectiveness (VE) against any and severe COVID-19 before and during Omicron variants (A) in populations fully vaccinated with proxy mRNA and non-RNA vaccines, (B) in populations boosted with proxy mRNA and non-RNA vaccines 1B, single booster dose; 2B+, at least 2 booster doses; ----, any COVID-19; —, severe COVID-19.

CI: 23.2-44.7%) within 12-15 months and 32.4% (95% CI: 21.8-41.4%) within 9-12 months among individuals vaccinated with proxy mRNA and non-mRNA vaccines, respectively.

Additional analyses, conducted on populations fully vaccinated with type-specific vaccines, i.e., mRNA, adenoviral vector (AdV), and inactivated (InV) vaccines, confirmed, apart from the persistence of AdV-related protection against severe disease during Omicron variant prevalence, previous findings (Supplementary Figure 1S, Table 8S). While these protection rates decreased, within 9-10 months, to 55.1% (95% CI: 41.3-65.6%) for mRNA vaccination and 43.7% (95% CI: 34.2-51.9%) for InV vaccination, the AdV-related rate dropped to 16.8% (95% CI: -6.1 to 34.8%).

Booster immunization

Before the emergence of Omicron variants, a high level of protection against both any and severe COVID-19 was achieved through a single booster dose, as evidenced by the early VE rates of 94.4% and 98.0% for mRNA vaccines, and 77.0% and 97.3% for non-mRNA vaccines, respectively (Figure 2B, Supplementary Table 9S).

Additionally, over a period of 5-7 months, persistence limited to only mRNA booster doses was observed at levels of 88.2% (95% CI: 84.1-91.2%) against any COVID-19 and 83.5% (95% CI: 78.3-87.5%) against severe COVID-19.

A single booster significantly improved early protection against Omicron-related COVID-19 of any severity compared to full vaccination. However, the VE against any and severe COVID-19 exhibited subsequent declines, decreasing from 62.8% (95% CI: 59.8-65.5%) to 30.9% (95% CI: 25.5-35.8%), and from 92.7% (95% CI: 91.1-94.0%) to 74.9% (95% CI: 70.3-78.8%) within 5 months, to persist at 14.0% (95% CI: 8.1-19.6%) and 67.7% (95% CI: 61.6-72.8%) during 6-8 months after a single mRNA booster dose, respectively.

A booster dose of non-mRNA vaccines also led to an early increase in VE to 46.4% (95% CI: 33.7-56.7%) against any COVID-19 related to Omicron variants, which persisted at 24.9% (95% CI: 16.0-32.8%) over 3-7 months. A similar rate of protection was observed against severe disease, showing a decline from 84.8% (95% CI: 79.7-88.7%) to 63.9% (95% CI: 56.2-70.2%) during the 3-7 months.

As the level of protection conferred by single booster immunization gradually declined over time, an additional 2 or more

booster doses of exclusively mRNA-only vaccines (monovalent or bivalent) were administered during the surges of Omicron variants. At 1 month after at least 2 booster doses, the protection rates reached 51.3% (95% CI: 43.3–58.2%) against any COVID-19, and 89.5% (95% CI: 80.8–94.5%) against severe disease. However, the protection rates persisted at 29.5% (95% CI: 16.6–40.5%) against any COVID-19 during 5–6 months, and at 70.6% (95% CI: 45.2–84.2%) against severe COVID-19 for 6–7 months after a multiple-dose booster.

Furthermore, bivalent vaccines designed to cover either the early or late Omicron variants demonstrated a nonsignificant increase in VE against any or severe COVID-19 compared to monovalent mRNA vaccines targeting the ancestral variant. Multiple booster doses of the monovalent mRNA vaccine provided a 57.0% (95% CI: 16.7–77.9%) level of protection against any COVID-19 caused by late Omicron variants, while a bivalent mRNA vaccine nonsignificantly increased VE to 65.4% (95% CI: 32.6–82.2%) in the general adult population with no prior SARS-CoV-2 infection. Similarly, the levels of protection against severe COVID-19 were 81.6% (95% CI: 51.5–93.0%) for the multiple booster doses of the monovalent mRNA vaccine, and 85.0% (95% CI: 59.4–94.5%) for the bivalent mRNA vaccine in the same population (Supplementary Table 10S).

Partial immunization

Except for the pre-Omicron variants, the rates of protection against any COVID-19 were consistently low, regardless of the vaccine types, and ranged between 9.3% and 41.6% within 5 months of partial vaccination. A single dose of a proxy mRNA vaccine was able to provide protection levels related to pre-Omicron variants between 52.0% and 56.5% within 5 months since the partial vaccination. The effectiveness against severe COVID-19 varied between 44.0% and 66.2% regardless of the prevailing variants, over at least 3 months after mRNA or non-mRNA vaccination (Supplementary Table 11S, Supplementary Figure 2S).

Population aged >65 years

Specific analyses conducted in the population aged >65 years demonstrated a time-dependent vaccine effectiveness not inferior to that established for the population older than 18 years in terms of vaccine type, number of received doses, severity of COVID-19, and time before and during Omicron variants. The time-dependent VE in the older population was not lower than the lower limit of the 95% CI of VE for the general population aged >18 years, as shown in Supplementary Figure 3S.

Discussion

This meta-regression, conducted as part of Meta-COVANESS, aimed to comprehensively assess the time-dependent effectiveness of COVID-19 vaccination. The study outcomes are applicable to the general adult population including individuals vaccinated with both mRNA and non-mRNA vaccines.

The populations fully vaccinated with proxy mRNA vaccines showed a higher early protection rate of 87.2% against any COVID-19 related to pre-Omicron variants, compared to the 66.3% level of protection in those immunized with other vaccine types. However, this difference was not substantial in terms of effectiveness against severe COVID-19, with a documented VE of 92.7% for the proxy mRNA-vaccinated population, and 88.2% for the non-mRNA-vaccinated population. Similar outcomes were observed among individuals vaccinated with specific vaccine types, specifically mRNA, AdV, and InV vaccines only. These findings were consistent with the results of early clinical trials of commercial vaccines [19].

Within the first year of the implementation of full vaccination against COVID-19, the effectiveness against infection and/or disease significantly declined to 55.1% for proxy mRNA vaccines and 23.5% for non-mRNA vaccines, when non-Omicron variants were dominant. The presence of the moderate-to-high number of unique mutations in the spike protein allowed the Omicron variants to evade postvaccination immunity, resulting in an early protection rate of only 53.9% for proxy mRNA-vaccinated individuals and 33.5% for those vaccinated with non-mRNA vaccines. Furthermore, this short-term effectiveness gradually decreased to eventually wane within 6 months of full vaccination, regardless of whether mRNA or non-mRNA vaccines had been administered.

Fortunately, full vaccination provided stronger and more durable protection against hospitalization or death caused by pre-Omicron variants, as demonstrated by the protection rates of 80.9% and 67.2% during the 9 months following vaccination with proxy mRNA and non-mRNA vaccines, respectively. Although the emergence of Omicron variants led to a reduction in the level of early protection by less than 10%, it seemed that full vaccination could retain the potential for continuous prevention of severe COVID-19. However, the 20% decline in protection observed at 6 months persisted, reaching 32.4% between 9 and 12 months after non-mRNA vaccination, and 34.8% between 12 and 15 months after proxy mRNA vaccination.

Even though similar protection levels were observed in individuals vaccinated with either mRNA or inactivated vaccines, it is intriguing that the population did not maintain protection beyond 8 months after full vaccination with adenoviral vector vaccines during the Omicron variant period. It is highly probable that the decline in the protective efficacy of this vaccine type became notably pronounced after 8 months, as supported by study estimates [20,21].

The implementation of booster immunization was prioritized to mitigate the spread of late pre-Omicron variant (i.e., Delta variant) infections, particularly among the more vulnerable populations [9]. The additional mRNA or non-mRNA vaccine dose yielded promising results, with new effectiveness against any COVID-19 rising to 94.4% and 77.0%, respectively, during the surge of pre-Omicron variants. This single booster dose demonstrated benefits when compared to the effects of full vaccination.

It was hypothesized that this booster could enhance protection against both any and severe cases of COVID-19 amid the emergence of Omicron variants [22]. Despite the initially increased short-term protection, the VE subsequently decreased to levels similar to those achieved by full vaccination, regardless of vaccine type, within roughly 6 months.

The observed reduction in effectiveness served as a precursor to the implementation of multiple-dose booster immunization [23]. Furthermore, the continuous mutation of Omicron variants, often evading immunity acquired through either vaccination or natural infection, clearly highlighted the necessity to develop new vaccines [24,25]. These vaccines not only encompassed the ancestral variant but included both early and late Omicron variants. They were promptly developed as bivalent mRNA vaccines and introduced in the fall of 2022. With a limited number of estimates available for 2 or 3-dose boosters with mono- or bivalent mRNA vaccines, we aggregated the available data to assess the effectiveness of multiple booster immunization.

Interestingly, the short-term effectiveness was similar to, though not as high as, that documented after full vaccination or a single booster. The previous findings of time-dependent protection were reaffirmed, as the effectiveness decreased from 51.3% to 29.5% against any COVID-19 and from 89.5% to 70.6% against severe disease over a span of approximately 6 months.

However, we sought to determine – through an additional analysis assessing the effectiveness of multiple booster doses of mono-

valent vaccines, both with and without bivalent mRNA vaccines – what levels of protection could be conferred by bivalent vaccines. Intriguingly, no significant differences in protection were found between both vaccine types, as indicated by the outcomes associated with the late Omicron variants that emerged in the fall and winter of 2022. The levels of protection against any and severe COVID-19 were shown to be 57.0% and 81.6% following a monovalent booster dose, and 65.4% and 85.0% following a bivalent booster dose, respectively. This finding is consistent with the outcomes of observational studies as well as studies reporting borderline superiority of the post-vaccination immune response to bivalent vaccines against late Omicron variants [26,27]. However, several studies assessing the relative VE demonstrated a significantly greater effect of bivalent compared to monovalent vaccines [28,29]. This deviation may have been due to the comparison of the impact of monovalent versus bivalent vaccines at different times since vaccination and since the surge of various late Omicron variants.

Based on these findings, the WHO recommendations to use only monovalent vaccines containing the currently predominant variants are warranted [30]. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that the newly acquired protection could likely again remain time-dependent.

Partial single-dose vaccination provided moderate protection of around 50% against severe COVID-19, persisting for 3–6 months regardless of the prevailing variants. This could be a valuable strategy to mitigate susceptibility among the less vulnerable populations when vaccine supply is limited. However, further research is necessary to fully understand the durability of the effect of single-dose vaccination.

The limitations of our study could stem from the stratification of the variables under investigation. To ensure consistency of results, we aggregated the VE estimates related to both the pre-Omicron and Omicron variants. We believe that this approach aligns with the outcomes of other studies, which showed no substantial difference between the Delta and pre-Delta variants [13]. However, it is essential to note that this approach might have overlooked the potential variability of protection during the surge of especially Alpha and Delta variants as well as early and late Omicron variants [31,32]. Additionally, we categorized vaccines into two groups based on whether the population received both mRNA and non-mRNA vaccines, or exclusively non-mRNA vaccines, which could present another limitation of the study. However, considering that most of the population was vaccinated with various vaccine types, this approach better reflected the real-world scenario.

Furthermore, the estimates exhibited a decrease with the length of the follow-up period, necessitating the merging of endpoint estimates and expressing VE in relation to the time interval. In an effort to obtain definitive time-dependent outcomes, the meta-regression models were adjusted to study-related confounding and risk factors. The results are applicable to the general adult population who received quasi-homologous vaccination and were previously noninfected.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of observational studies, our study outcomes unequivocally demonstrated a progressive time-linked decline in the effectiveness of COVID-19 vaccination. While the declining effectiveness of full vaccination was restored by a single booster dose and persisted during the prevailing pre-Omicron variants, booster immunization during the surge of the Omicron variant, whether with a single dose or multiple doses, inadequately prevented the diminishing protection against COVID-19 of varying severity over time. A feasible solution may indeed require the development and introduction of novel monovalent vaccines targeting the currently dominant variants of the coronavirus.

Declarations of competing interest

We declare no competing interests.

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Author contributions

MP, PD, and JR conceptualized the study. MP, DJ, DL, and IKL curated the data. MF carried out the literature search and data collection. MP did the formal data analysis. MP contributed to the methodology. PD and IKL ensured funding acquisition. MP administered the project. MP supervised the project. MP wrote the original draft, and all authors contributed to data interpretation and writing, reviewing, and editing this manuscript.

Data sharing

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.ijid.2024.106986](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2024.106986).

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